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Identification of circular eco-subsystems for end-of-life aviation composite components based on a systematized R6-strategy

P Johst¹, M Kucher¹, P Schulz², A Knorr³, R Kupfer², R Böhm¹

¹ Leipzig University of Applied Sciences, Faculty of Engineering, Leipzig, Germany

² Technische Universität Dresden, Institute of Lightweight Engineering and Polymer Technology (ILK), Dresden, Germany

³ Elbe Flugzeugwerke GmbH (EFW), Dresden, Germany

E-mail: philipp.johst@htwk-leipzig.de

Abstract. The demand of composites in the aviation and space industry has increased significantly in recent decades. This is due to the excellent properties of composite materials, especially their low density and design flexibility. However, the reuse and further utilization of composite structures and their materials provide new challenges for the recycling sector. In accordance with the 'Green Deal' of the European Commission, new pathways are required to ensure an effective and economic reuse of composite components at their end-of-life (EoL). We discuss a strategic approach for returning decommissioned parts of aviation composites back into the material cycle with a particular focus on waste reduction, as well as the decrease of the associated energy demand and emissions. Therefore, a sustainable strategy to exploit various circular possibilities was applied, consisting of the six R-strategies: *reuse*, *repair*, *refurbish*, *remanufacture*, *repurpose* and *recycling*. The Multi-Tiered System of Support is transferred to the introduced R6-strategy. The concept provides an approach to address the challenges of reintroducing EoL composites into the material chain. Based on the systematized R6-strategy it was possible to identify circular eco-subsystems for aviation composite components with minimal effort. Finally, this paper discusses a potential criterion used for assigning EoL aviation composites to the various eco-subsystems.

1. Introduction

The aviation and space industry has a high demand of composite materials. This can be attributed to first-rate component properties like low density, reduced maintenance effort, improved fatigue life, high mechanical stiffness and strength adaptability according to the applied loads. Currently, a high amount of EoL materials is available for recycling from the aviation and space industry [1]. For instance, the fuselage of the Boeing 787 consists of up to 50 % weight of composites [2]. This results in an estimated total mass of 23.360 t/year of EoL carbon fibre-reinforced polymers (CFRP) if these materials are not recycled by 2035. Today, about 60 % of fibre-reinforced polymers (FRP) are landfilled across all industries [3].

However, the decommissioned composite components will provide new challenges for the recycling sector. The use of high-performance thermosets makes the recycling of fibres and resin difficult [4]. In order to pursue the path set by the European Union's (EU) 'Green Deal' [5], new approaches are needed to ensure effective and economic multiple use of EoL composite

components. Innovative design and logistical concepts for reusing and recycling composites - from whole components over sub-structural parts to granular material and powders - must be developed and implemented to make the aviation and space industry more sustainable [6].

To date, closed-loop product chains are seen as the solution to realize sustainability since they can help preserve resources by applying materials multiple times. The used recycling technologies must ensure that the material maintains its original quality at the end of each cycle. For composite materials, recycling technologies still need to be developed further and introduced into the market. Existing solutions are not easily adaptable to large-scale or hybrid composite parts like aircraft components. Furthermore, they are still not cost competitive [7, 8] and the mechanical properties of recycled FRP usually decrease [9]. Therefore, an assessment method for EoL composite structure's material properties has to be provided to quantify the material degradation [10]. For this, suitable degradation models are required [11, 12, 13, 14]. Due to the outlined circumstances it is commonly accepted, that only focussing on recycling will not allow the implementation of an energy efficient and resource-conserving circular economy for composites [15]. Other treatment strategies (R-strategies) beyond recycling are becoming more relevant for composite structures.

This article discusses a strategic circular approach for the multiple use of EoL aviation composites. It consists of six treatment strategies selected from the established 9R-strategy [15]. The R6-strategy aims to reduce the landfill of EoL aviation composites as well as the usage of incineration processes and thereby minimizing the negative environmental impact [16]. In addition, the interdependencies between the six R-strategies are discussed. Based on a systematized R6-strategy, circular eco-subsystems with minimal effort are identified.

2. Method

According to Potting et al. [15] there are ten R-strategies available to implement the strategic circular approach for aviation composites. They aim to extend a product's lifespan, to reduce natural resource consumption and to minimize emissions [17]. The R-strategies *refuse* (R0), *rethink* (R1), *reduce* (R2) and *recover* (R9) are not expedient for the context of this article. R0, R1 and R2 refer to product planning. R9 implies the incineration of materials. This means that it is not a closed-loop strategy since the composites vanish after this treatment strategy. To formulate the circular R6-strategy for large scale aviation composites, the R-strategies given and defined in Table 1 are selected.

Table 1. Definition of selected R-strategies (compare e.g. [15])

R-strategy	Definition
Reuse	Reuse by another consumer of discarded product which is still in good condition and fulfils its original function.
Repair	Repair and maintenance of defective product so it can be used with its original function.
Refurbish	Restore an old product or part and bring it up to date.
Remanufacture	Use parts of discarded product in a new product with the same function.
Repurpose	Use discarded product or its parts in a new product with a different function.
Recycling	Process materials to obtain the same (high grade) or lower (low grade) quality.

Based on the general approaches outlined in the literature, the interactions between the different R-strategies have to be considered in the context of multiple composite material use. To prioritize the treatment strategies and to systematize the R6-strategy, the Multi-Tiered System of Support (MTSS) is adopted. The MTSS¹ is a system that includes a continuum of intervention methods on three tiers to ensure adaptive supports for students to maximize learning outcomes. Further, it helps teachers in choosing the most efficient intervention method [18]. The MTSS framework is in line with the R6-strategy as it provides an approach to address the challenges of EoL composite treatment. In the context of MTSS, the R-strategies can be applied on three tiers to ensure the appropriate implementation of the various R-strategies that lead to positive environmental outcomes [18, 20]. The adoption of the MTSS creates a Multi-Tiered System of Treatment (MTS-T), and therefore, a systematized R6-strategy. With the systematization, the R-strategies are prioritized and assigned to various tiers. The systematized R6-strategy approach consists of closed-loops and is equivalent with a circular ecosystem. The circular ecosystem for aviation composites is a complex constellation of actors, technologies and institutions that are bound together via interdependencies to produce sustainable composite products [21]. The systematized R6-strategy consists of prioritized R-strategies and three tiers. To apply the R-strategies within the assigned tiers, a different actor, technology and institution constellations are required. Due to this, it is possible to identify circular eco-subsystems for aviation composites.

3. Results and discussion

In the context of the circularity of aviation composite components the six R-strategies are not mutually exclusive, but should be considered as harmonizing strategies supporting each other.

3.1. R6-strategy

Figure 1 inspired by [22] shows the interactions between the different R-strategies.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the interactions of the R6-strategy's treatments.

¹ Education researchers and schools designed the MTSS. It is typically implemented to help teachers decide which intervention to choose in a difficult situation [18, 19].

First, the EoL composites are sorted according to quality thresholds using collected data. Next, the decommissioned and classified parts are assigned to the various possible treatment strategies of the R6-strategy. Potting et al. [15] refer to products, whereas this article only focuses on composite parts of a product. Therefore, *reuse* is only effective in combination with other R-strategies (see Figure 1). Rather, *reuse* requires the reintegration of composite parts into another product. This is explained in detail further below:

- The *repair* strategy aims to extend the service life of a aviation composite application by using minimal resources like patches during the operation process.
- To *refurbish* an old composite part means that it is restored to make it usable for a specific application again.
- In the *remanufacturing* loop, the goal is the reuse. For example, turning an old composite aircraft structure into a new aircraft application. To achieve this goal, it can be necessary to repair or refurbish the component to perform its original function in the new product, i.e. by improving the surface finish for a non-structural application.
- The *repurposing* strategy can be used for aircraft composite parts or even entire aircrafts for repurposed uses, such as furniture, artwork or hotels inside of an aircraft fuselage [23]. In addition, the repair or refurbish strategy may be required for the reuse by repurposing of a composite part as a structural application which must endure high mechanical loads.
- For *recycling*, fibre and matrix of the composite material have to be separated as well as any additional materials from e.g. sealings, inserts or coatings. This treatment strategy should also be considered for composite waste generated during manufacturing processes. The recycling technologies of composites can be divided into mechanical, thermal and chemical approaches [4].

3.2. Systematisation of the R6-strategy

The MTS-T (Figure 2 inspired by [20] and [24]) was developed by applying the model and basic principles of the aforementioned MTSS to systematize the R6-strategy.

Figure 2. Schematic representation of the systematized R6-strategy.

The systematized R6-strategy consists of the following key components:

- i) Sorting based on 'Quality Thresholds' - Continuous data collection and screening of decommissioned composites to assess the condition and to assign the components in appropriate tiers.
- ii) Three tiers of treatment involving specific R-strategies in response to the condition of EoL composites.
- iii) Constant monitoring of the performed R-strategies.

Figure 2 shows the three tiers of treatment that comprise the selected R-strategies. The first tier *prevention and repair* aims to maximize the service life of the composite components. Avoiding EoL composites requires changes in manufacturing technologies and the design of the composite application [16]. The modification should be done in a way that the expected changes of the composite material during the service life are minimal and the materials can be kept in the cycles as long as possible [25]. The availability of material data for processing and performing structural simulation is a crucial factor in enabling high prediction accuracy of the composite behaviour [26]. A combination of established characterization methods and new measurement approaches are required. For example, sensors that provide valuable online data during the service life of the aviation application. With the help of this data, specific planning of repair activities is possible and can ensure that the expected service life is achieved [8].

The second tier is referred to as *reuse and recycling*. The composite structure has to be used and reused as much as possible before it is classified as non-treatable EoL composites. Reuse by refurbishing, remanufacturing or repurposing can potentially prevent large quantities of materials from entering unsustainable waste streams such as landfill [27, 28]. The material data generated during the service life of the application can be used to define the general guidelines for designing structures to reuse EoL components. To carry out this strategy, it may be beneficial to repair or refurbish localized areas of the composite parts. If reuse by refurbishing, remanufacturing or repurposing is no longer possible, recycling should be the following prioritized treatment strategy. Compared to glass fibre-reinforced polymers, CFRP are financially more affordable for recycling because of the higher costs of the carbon fibres. Therefore, the costs depend on the material composition. Recycled CFRP will be more attractive if the mechanical properties do not decrease during the recycling processes. In this context, the downscaling of carbon fibres has to be considered. It should be noted that the quality of the recycled materials decreases with each recycling loop [29].

If none of the previously mentioned treatment strategies are applicable, incineration or disposal are the last options. The assignment of EoL aviation composites to the third tier should be kept to a minimum since it removes the composite materials from the circular material chain.

The presented systematized R6-strategy (Figure 1 and Figure 2) results from the current development of the recycling technologies for composites. The recycling strategy is expected to become more important as recycled materials' effectiveness, quality, and cost-competitiveness increase. In line with the EU's 'Green Deal' [5], the aim is to ensure the collaborative use of the systematized R6-strategy and the exploitation of its advantages for the future use of FRP components in the aviation and space industry. Currently, the legislative framework must be more convincing to encourage European economic circularity. There are many barriers to overcome on a national and European level. Because of this legal situation, there is a need to develop a framework that stays in line with the holistic approach of the proposed systematized R6-strategy. Landfill bans, taxes or carbon footprint measuring of manufactured products could act as a driver for the treatment and disposal of composite products to change industrial practices [8]. Furthermore, it is crucial to investigate how previous life cycles and treatment strategies influence material properties [30]. Therefore, continuous monitoring of the

implemented treatment strategies according to the R6-strategy is required at all steps of the circular ecosystem for composite materials.

3.3. Identification of circular eco-subsystems

A change in the tier of the systematized R6-strategy results in different actors, technologies and institutions that are responsible for the implementation of the treatment strategies. Within the first tier, for instance, a company specialized in repairing composite components is appointed as main actor. In comparison, a recycling company is primarily responsible for the treatment strategy of recycling on the second tier. Therefore, the circular eco-subsystems of *repair*, *reuse* and *recycling* were identified. These eco-subsystems represent closed loops, starting with sorting EoL aviation composites guiding a multiple use of the composite materials. In order to select the most sufficient eco-subsystem, a close coordination of available material resources and information flows are required between all individual stakeholders within the eco-subsystem. Active engagement from all the players is needed which considers the protection of the company's specific know-how to develop cost-effective solutions and strong European value chains.

The most crucial decision criterion is the damage condition of the EoL aviation composites. A component with small damages should be repaired to extend the service life of the application. If repairing a small damaged composite structure is not technically feasible, reuse will be considered. This represents the permeability of the three tiers of the systematized R6-strategy. Moderate damaged composite structures will be considered for the eco-subsystem of reuse. If high damage occurs on the composite components and the eco-subsystem of repair and reuse cannot be realized, the recycling loop should be the next prioritized treatment strategy.

The logistical effort required to relocate the EoL aviation components must guide the decision for the most appropriate eco-subsystem. The logistical effort has to be widely effective to avoid additional costs and emissions. This can be achieved, in particular, through the establishment of a local infrastructure for reuse and recycling of composite structures. Thereby, both the production locations and the application locations of composite structures must be considered.

4. Conclusion

A circular strategic approach was proposed for returning decommissioned composite parts to the material chain. It consists of: *reuse*, *repair*, *refurbish*, *remanufacture*, *repurpose* and *recycling*. The proposed systematized R6-strategy aims for EoL composite reduction, consequent energy and emission savings. Based on the approach, circular eco-subsystems of *repair*, *reuse* and *recycling* have been identified. These eco-subsystems are closed loops that originate in the sorting to reach a multiple use of the aviation composite components. Close coordination of available material resources and information flows related to EoL material data is required among the various stakeholders within the entire composite material ecosystem. For the allocation of EoL aviation composites to the different eco-subsystems, the damage condition of the components is the most critical decision criterion. The proportion of non-treatable composite waste should be reduced by an appropriate assignment of the aviation composites to the tiers.

At this stage, the legislative framework needs to be more convincing to encourage such an economic circularity in Europe. Nevertheless, the strategic approach presented in this article provides valuable input for the reuse and recycling of aviation composite structures.

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